

Meiotic chromosomes of male progeny derived from *N. virescens* parents caged on TN1 rice plants treated with 500 and 2,500 ppm NSB, IRRI, 1987. a) Metaphase arrest, b) chromosome stickiness and elongation.

parents (set table). The arrest of metaphase I stage in meiotic chromosomes of primary spermatocytes (see figure) was most evident at 500 and 2,500 ppm NSB. Of 450 meiocytes, about 40-60% were at first metaphase. The meiotic cells of progeny derived from treated parents lacked the ample spindle fibers needed for normal disjunction of chromosomes during succeeding stages of spermatogenesis. About 18 and 21% chromosomal abnormalities were caused in treatments with 500 and 2,500 ppm NSB,

respectively. At 500 ppm, meiotic cells showed 10% chromosome elongation and 8% reduction in chromosome number due to autosomal stickiness and fusions. At 2,500 ppm, chromosome elongations were 13% and chromosome fusions 8%. The reduced reproductive fitness of *N. virescens* caged on rice plants treated with neem derivatives can be attributed to cellular and chromosomal dysfunctions during spermatogenesis, leading to nonviability and senescence of sperm cells. □

Thrips control at tillering of transplanted rice

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Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* Bagnall causes severe damage to seedlings in the nursery and to the transplanted crop in the main field at tillering. We evaluated 5 new insecticides — 3 granular and 2 spray formulations — for thrips control in a field experiment during thaladi season (Oct 86–Feb 87). Checks were

Table 1. Effect of new insecticides on thrips control. TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1986.

Insecticide	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Thrips ^a (no./10 hand passes) at 3 DAT
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	14.8 ab
Cartap4G	1.5	16.3 b
Ethoprop 10 G	1.5	13.5 ab
Carbofuran 3 G (standard check)	1.0	14.0 ab
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.5	13.5 ab
Dadeci 5.9 EC (decamethrin 150 g + buprofezin 9 g)	0.09	15.3 ab
Phosalone 35 EC (standard check)	0.5	12.5 a
No insecticide (untreated check)		22.0 c

^a Mean of 3 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level, based on CD value. DAT = days after treatment.

Table 2. Effect of granular and spray formulations of insecticides on thrips control. TRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1986.

Insecticide	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Thrips ^a (no./10 hand passes) at 3 DAT
Phosphamidon 85 EC	0.5	13 ab
Monocrotophos 40 EC	0.5	14 ab
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	0.5	9 a
Quinalphos 25 EC	0.5	17 ab
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.5	20 bc
Phosalone 35 EC	0.5	17 ab
Carbofuran 3 G	1.0	34 c
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	20 bc
BHC 10 D 25 kg/ha		18 ab
No insecticide (untreated check)		25 bc

^a Mean of 3 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level based on CD value. DAT = days after treatment.

carbofuran 3G and phosalone 35 EC. Rice variety IR20 was grown. Insecticides were applied at 20 d after

transplanting (DT) and at 40 DT, if thrips incidence was found.

In a second field experiment, insecticides commonly used to control different rice pests were evaluated for thrips control. They were applied at 38 DT if thrips population and damage were observed.

Thrips populations were sampled by a field worker passing his wet palm over leaves at 10 places/plot; damage was sampled by counting total and affected leaves on 10 hills/plot at 3 and 14 d after first insecticide application.

Spray formulations of chlorpyrifos 40 EC at 0.5 kg ai/ha and Dadeci 5.9 EC at 0.09 kg ai/ha, and granular ethoprop at 1.5 kg ai/ha were as effective as the standard checks for controlling thrips damage (Table 1).

Chlorpyrifos 20 EC at 0.5 kg ai/ha significantly reduced thrips populations 3 d after spraying (Table 2). □

Cytogenetic effects of neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) on brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* spermatocytes

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Exposure to neem *Azadirachta indica* seed derivatives is known to reduce the reproductive potential of several insect pest species. We investigated the effect

on reproductive fitness of first generation male progeny of BPH male and female parents caged on rice plants sprayed with 100 or 500 ppm of aqueous NSKE.

Primary and secondary spermatocytes of BPH progeny collected from NSKE-treated and untreated plants were examined using the lacto-aceto-orcein squash technique. Frequency of meiotic cells was significantly less in progeny collected from NSKE-treated plants.